

EFFECT OF FLEXIBILITY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF POLYMERIC FOAMS IN SANDWICH CONSTRUCTION HULL PANELLING UNDER SLAMMING

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Keywords: Sandwich construction, Slamming, Marine, Flexibility, Hydroelasticity

ABSTRACT

Prediction of damage to hull panelling during dynamic slamming impacts is critical in the design of safe vessels. Modern composite hull design often utilises high ductility polymeric foams in a sandwich construction for regions likely to undergo slamming during operation. The nature of these constructions, which have large failure strains compared with metallic constructions, can result in panelling that undergoes significant deformations during slamming impacts. These deformations have been shown to affect the applied pressure distribution and magnitude. This paper addresses how the stress state in the core varies as a result of flexibility in hull panelling.

Experiments have been undertaken on a range of sandwich construction panels using the custom Servo-hydraulic Slam Testing System (SSTS). Rectangular glass-fibre/epoxy skin sandwich panel specimens of dimensions 1030±5 mm x 540±05 mm were manufactured using a resin infusion process with Gurit M130 as their core material. The thickness of the GRP skins was varied between panels. Testing has been undertaken on the panels at 10° with vertical impact velocities between 1.0 m/s and 9.5 m/s. The panel's integrity is monitored throughout the impacts using bi-axial resistive strain gauges. The velocities at which both yield and ultimate failure occur have been identified.

Variations in both the yield and failure speeds of the panels have been observed experimentally. These variations are linked to the varying levels of deformation between the panels resulting in different pressure distributions. These findings highlight the necessity to consider both strength and stiffness in scenarios where fluid-structure interaction may be present as a change in stiffness may lead to an inadvertent change in effective strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dynamic free surface water impacts are a common occurrence for ocean going vessels. The severity of the impact depends on the velocity and angle at which the hull enters the water. Dynamic free surface water impacts, commonly referred to as hull slamming, present one of the greatest design load cases for marine vessel. Structural predictions of a hulls performance to these events are therefore critical for safe and optimal design. Substantial research has been undertaken to characterise the pressures and loads during slamming impacts as well as the structural response of impacting structures, this work has been well summarise by Abrate [1]

Elasticity in impacting hull panelling can have a significant effect on the pressures and loads [2]. These differences are linked to hydroelasticity during the impact. Hydroelasticity is the dynamic fluid-structure interaction between an impacting body and the body of water. Existing research into hydroelasticity has focused on the variations in the pressures and loads during slamming impacts. To date the effect of the hydroelasticity on the structural response has only had minimal attention. Previous work by the authors [2,3] has shown that flexibility in hull panelling shifts the centre of pressure towards the outer edge of the hull panelling leading to greater transverse shear forces. The aim of this work is to establish if this shift in centre of pressure due to hydroelasticity affects the structural performance of the polymeric foams in sandwich constructions during slamming impacts.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experiments have been undertaken using the University of Auckland's Servo-hydraulic Slam Testing System (SSTS), Figure 1. This was custom designed and developed by Industrial Research Limited, Auckland, NZ and the University of Auckland and utilises a sophisticated high speed servo-hydraulic system to control the motion of a panel structure during impact with the water. Details of the system are described by Battley and Allen [4]. The SSTS has been extensively used for characterisation of water impacts. [4-7].

The SSTS uses a cylindrical water tank with a diameter of 3.5 m and a water depth of typically 1.4 m, giving a fluid domain of approximately 13,500L. A steel frame supports the hydraulic ram, manifold, servo-valve, accumulators and associated plumbing above the tank. The specimen fixture (see Figure 2), which is attached to the hydraulic ram, slides on vertical rails and hence moves in one degree of freedom. The system is designed for testing panel specimens approximately 1000 × 500 mm. Two hydraulic accumulators supply oil to the ram and the velocity is controlled by a servo-valve and a closed-loop PID controller using position and acceleration feedback. Three vertical panels, two on the sides and one behind the panel constrain the flow along the panel. The SSTS can achieve velocities of up to approximately 10 m/s. The specialised servo-hydraulic hardware is controlled by a MOOG™ MSC 3000 electronic controller and custom developed software to achieve the required combination of high velocity, force, and accurate control of motion during the slamming event.

Figure 1 Servo-hydraulic Slam Testing System

Figure 2 Schematic of specimen fixture and flow control panels 1-Specimen Fixture, 2-Linear bearings and tracks, 3- Aluminium support frame, 4- Flow restriction panels

2.1 Test specimens

Four sandwich construction specimens have been constructed using resin infusion. Each of the panels is constructed using 20 mm Gurit M130 foam with biaxial glass reinforced epoxy skins. The cloth used is 825 gsm. The specifications of the four panels are given in Table 1. Based on Zenkert [8] panels can be approximated as thin face sandwiches with weak cores if they satisfy Equations 1 and 2 respectively.

$$\frac{d}{t_f} > 5.77 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{6E_f t_f d^2}{E_c t_c^3} > 100 \quad (2)$$

Based on the thin face and weak core approximations it is assumed that the faces carry the applied bending moments in tension and compression and the core carries the transverse forces as shear stresses. By altering the lay-up of the skins between each of the panels the flexural rigidity, D , is changed with only small variations in the nominal shear strength. The maximum shear stress able to be carried by the sandwich is given by classical sandwich theory as Equation 3.

$$\tau_{max} = \frac{T_y}{d} \quad (3)$$

Traditional methods of predicting the loads and pressure distribution during slamming impacts do not consider the effect of flexibility in the hull panelling, therefore using these predictions for calculation of failure would lead to all panels failing under the same load conditions. The 'as manufactured' properties of the panels have been established through measurement of the core and skin thicknesses and calculation of flexural rigidity, D , and shear stiffness, S .

Panel ID	t_c [mm]	t_f [mm]	D [Nm]	S [kN/m]
Soft	18.8	1.6	5660	1310
Medium #1	19.7	2.2	8970	1440
Medium #2	19.5	2.2	8810	1420
Stiff	18.9	3.2	13300	1520

Table 1: Panel properties

2.2 Experimental test matrix

All testing for this work was undertaken with a deadrise angle (the angle between the panel and the water surface) of 10°. The first impact had a vertical impact velocity of 1.0 m/s. Each subsequent impact had an increase in target velocity of 0.5 m/s. The maximum impact velocities for the panel were 9.0, 8.5, 9.5 and 8.0 m/s. The maximum velocities were determined by monitoring failure of the panel visually and via resistive strain gauges adhered to the inside skin of the panel. A summary of the test matrix is given in Table 2.

Panel ID	Angle [°]	Impact velocities [m/s]
Soft	10	1.0 – 8.0
Medium #1	10	1.0 – 8.5
Medium #2	10	1.0 – 9.5
Stiff	10	1.0 – 9.0

Table 2: Test matrix

2.3 Specimen instrumentation

Each panel has been instrumented with two biaxial strain gauges (TML FCA-6-11 120Ω), located as in Figure 3. The strain gauges are located at the centre of the unsupported region of the panel and 35 mm in from the chine edge of the panel. The chine edge is taken as the long edge of the panel which is submerged last during the impact.

Figure 3: Instrumentation schematic, gauges denoted by arrows

3 FAILURE PREDICTION

For the purposes of design it is important to be able to predict the failure of hull panelling under slamming loads. Traditional approaches approximate the load applied to the panel as a uniform static pressure, from which a stress state in the core can be established. Design codes have semi-empirical methods for determining the pressure magnitudes based on vessel dimensions and design parameters. [9,10] This method of determining the relevant design pressure is not applicable for a single panel specimen. Analytical solutions for the applied force can however be used to calculate an equivalent uniform pressure. Wagner [11] presented such a formula for total force, given here in Equation 4. This can be equated to a uniform pressure, given in Equation 5.

$$F_w = \frac{ab\rho\pi^2v^2}{2\sin(\beta)} \quad (4)$$

$$P_w = \frac{\rho\pi^2v^2}{4\sin(\beta)\cos(\beta)} \quad (5)$$

A similar prediction has been presented by von Karman [12]. Equation 6 presents the calculation for an equivalent uniform pressure based on von Karman's force prediction.

$$P_{vk} = \frac{\rho\pi v^2}{2\sin(\beta)\cos(\beta)} \quad (6)$$

Previous work [3] has highlight how the relationship between the maximum bending moment and shear force varies in sandwich panels undergoing slamming loads compared with a uniformly loaded panel. The ratio between maximum shear to bending was estimated to be between 15.5 and 18.0, compared with a value of 9.43 for a panel under a uniform load with an aspect ratio of 2:1, as tested in this work. This variation in shear to bending ratio is critical when considering various failure modes. For instance when considering core failure due to transverse shear forces the higher shear force relative to bending moment may lead to premature yield or failure. Figure 4 and Figure 5

Figure 4: Experimental maximum moments in the x direction compared with analytical predictions [3]

Figure 5: Peak experimental transverse shear forces compared with analytical predictions [3]

The maximum transverse shear force can be determined based on Zenkert's calculation [8] for a 2:1 aspect ratio sandwich panel under uniform load with 4 simply supported boundaries, given in Equation 7. The pressure magnitude, q , can either be taken directly from Equation 5 or 6. Alternatively it can be modified based on Allen and Battley [3].

$$T_y = 0.452qb \quad (7)$$

Maximum transverse shear stress has been taken from the Gurit M130 Datasheet, which gives it as 1.93MPa. This value is based on ASTM C273, a block shear test. The shape of the shear stress-strain curves during testing to ASTM C273 for Gurit M130, as undertaken by Clark [13], indicates the peak stress occurs close to the start of plastic deformation of the foam. Therefore this value is effectively yield strength, with plastic deformation occurring beyond this load level. The testing by Clark [13] also highlighted how the test method and speed can affect the apparent shear strength of polymeric foam materials, including Gurit M130. These differences will be constant for all of the panels as the material is consistent between them, furthermore the same work showed little variation in the performance of Gurit M130 over the strain rates relevant to water impacts, albeit higher than the static performance.

Table 3 presents the impact velocity at which each panels is predicted to yield. The slight variations between the panels is due to differences in d , as given in Table 1. Values have been given both based on Wagner (Equation 5) and von Karman (Equation 6), both in their original form and modified based on Allen and Battley [3].

Panel ID	Wagner		von Karman	
	Original	Modified	Original	Modified
Soft	3.53	2.75	4.42	3.45
Medium #1	3.66	2.85	4.58	3.57
Medium #2	3.64	2.83	4.56	3.55
Stiff	3.67	2.86	4.60	3.58

Table 3: Predict velocity (m/s) at which panel yield occurs

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results of the panel testing in the SSTS can be used to identify when yield or failure has occurred in the specimen. These failure velocities can be compared with the predicted values given in Table 3. As discussed earlier, other work [2] has shown a variation is expected in the pressure

distribution based on the flexibility of the impacting structure. Based on that work the prediction is that the panels will fail in order of stiffness with the least stiff panel failing first.

Figure 6 presents strains measured in the X and Y directions (as defined in Figure 3) at the centre and chine edge on the medium #2 panel during an impact with an average impact velocity of 4.2 m/s. Inspection of the panel after impact at this velocity indicated no signs of damage, with the panel remaining flat and no visible through thickness cracks. The largest strain measured is at the centre of the panel in the Y direction, 3500 microstrain. The maximum strain measured at the chine edge (1400 microstrain) is also in the Y direction. There is a substantial difference in the shape of the strain curves (Y direction) between the centre and the chine. The centre shows a gradual increase up to the peak, while at the chine edge there is a much more sudden increase between 13 and 15 ms. The strain in the X direction is much lower at both the centre and chine edge. In both cases there is a slight delay in the strain in the X direction when compared with the peak in the Y direction. The strain in the X direction at the chine appears negligible. These trends are consistent for all impacts, on all panels, for impact velocities below where damage occurred.

Figure 6: Strains measured on medium (#1) stiffness panel during 4.2 m/s impact

Damage can be easily identified by comparing the strain plots across a range of impact velocities, noting any variations for the trends observed at lower impact velocities. Figure 7 presents plots of strains for a range of impact velocities, from no damage to complete failure and through thickness shear cracking in the core. Figure 7(a) shows little variation from the traces presented in Figure 6. There is a slight non-zero value at the start of the event for the strain in the X direction at the chine edge in Figure 7(b). This indicates there is potentially some residual plastic deformation, likely in the foam core in the region on the chine edge. Figure 7(c) shows an even larger non-zero initial strain, suggesting greater levels of plastic deformation. The peak chine strain in the Y direction also increases dramatically to being greater than the Y direction strain at the centre of the panel. Figure 7(d) shows a substantial change in the strain profiles, indicating a catastrophic failure of the core. This failure was confirmed later as a through thickness crack, as shown in Figure 8. The photo shows one half of the panel sectioned into 4 pieces.

Figure 7: Strains measured on medium (#1) stiffness panel across a range of impact velocities

Figure 8: Photo of sectioned panel showing through thickness shear cracks (chine edge on left)

These changes in the strain traces can be utilized to compare when each of the panels begin to yield and fail. The best measures of these changes have been determined to be the variation in the peak for in the Y direction at the chine and the residual strain at the chine in either the X or Y direction.

4.1 Peak chine strain (Y direction)

Figure 9 presents the maximum strain at the chine in the Y direction. At low impact velocities there is little change in the peak Y direction chine strains between each of the panels. All panels have a similar magnitude and trend up to approximately 5.5 m/s. Each panel at some point then deviates from

this trend, showing a dramatic increase in peak strain. The sharp increase in chine peak strain seen in Figure 7(c) is clearly shown in Figure 9 for the medium #1 panel, between 6.65 and 7.38 m/s.

Figure 9: Maximum Y direction strain at the chine edge of each of the panels

The stiffer the panel is the higher the velocity is at which the strains deviate from the trend. This is a strong indicator that the stiffness of the panel influences the velocity at which plastic deformation and failure occur. Table 4 summarizes the velocities where the peak strains for each of the panels begins to deviate.

Panel ID	Yield velocity
Soft	5.5 m/s
Medium #1	6.0 m/s
Medium #2	6.7 m/s
Stiff	8.0 m/s

Table 4: Panel yield based on peak Y strain at chine edge

4.2 Residual strain

For impacts where the yield stress of the M130 is exceeded, plastic deformation occurs. This plastic deformation induces a residual stress into the glass reinforced epoxy skins. Measurement of the strain between each test provides a quantitative measure of the level of deformation in the core. Glass reinforced epoxy is known to have negligible plasticity and the strains are well below that expected for damage in the skins, therefore the residual stress present will not be from plasticity or failure in the skins.

Figure 10 presents the residual strain in both the X and Y direction measured at the chine edge of the panel. These values have been taken from the start of the following test prior to any motion, i.e. the value for the 1 m/s impact is taken from the start of the 1.5 m/s impact. This represents a 5 min waiting period between the impact and the measurement of the residual strain. It is possible some relaxation occurs in this period, however with equal waiting times between tests the effect of this relaxation can be neglected.

Figure 10: Residual strains at the chine edge in the (a) X direction and (b) Y direction

Table 5 summaries the velocities where the residual become non-zero. The results are similar to those based on the peak Y strain at the chine edge in that the trend appears to be higher failure velocities for stiffer panels. Of note is that the medium # 2 panel shows residual strain in the X direction as well as the Y direction, highlighting the potential for a complex stress state in the core close to the chine edge of the panel.

Panel ID	X direction	Y direction
Soft	N/A	4.3 m/s
Medium #1	N/A	5.8 m/s
Medium #2	6.2 m/s	6.2 m/s
Stiff	N/A	6.5 m/s

Table 5: Panel yield based on residual X & Y strain at chine edge

4.3 Peak centre strain

Similarly to the chine, the strains at the centre can be considered. These strains will be more heavily affected by the flexural rigidity of the panel, independent of the hydroelasticity, than the strains at the chine edge of the panel. Figure 11 presents the maximum strain at the centre of the panel in the X and Y directions. No discernable point of variation can be seen in Figure 11(a) in the maximum strain in the X direction at the centre of the panel. A gradual increase in the X direction strain at the centre of the panel is expected. As the panel begins to yield it is expected that more of the load is carried in the long direction of the panel. In the Y direction there is a velocity after which the maximum strain decreases. This is likely after the point at which a crack develops in the core. Similar to the maximum strain in the Y direction at the chine edge of the panel, there is a trend of the stiffer the panel, the higher the velocity at which the highest strain is recorded.

Figure 11: Maximum X & Y direction strain at the centre of the panels

5 CONCLUSIONS

Experimental water impacts on panels with a range of stiffness, but approximately equal transverse shear strength, have been undertaken. Strains measured on the inner skin of the sandwich composite have been used to compare the velocities at which failure and/or yield begins within the polymeric foam core. Analysis of the strain time histories over the event period for a range of impact velocities has highlighted the key measures for determining when the panel begins to behave differently, inferring plastic deformation in the core. These measures are peak strain in the transverse (Y) direction at the chine edge of the panel and residual strain in both the transverse (Y) and longitudinal (X) directions at the chine.

Comparison of both the peak and residual strains indicates there is a trend between increasing stiffness and increasing failure velocity. The difference observed between stiffest and most flexible is between 2.2 and 2.5 m/s depending on which measure is considered.

This trend of decreased strength for more flexible panels is believed to be due to a variation in the pressure distribution when impacting structures undergo deformation, illustrated in previous research by the authors [2,14]. The change in pressure distribution results in higher shear forces relative to bending moments for more flexible panels. The strength of sandwich constructions, which are more susceptible to transverse shear failure, is therefore adversely affected. This conclusion cannot be extended to monolithic structures, which typically have more bending dominated failures.

6 FUTURE WORK

The range of panels considered here is very limited, with the flexural rigidity only varying from 5,660 to 13,300 Nm and only a single repeat undertaken for the most and least flexible panels. A more in depth experimental test matrix would be required to draw definitive conclusions regarding the relationship between stiffness and failure. Additionally testing of monolithic structures should be tested to determine the effect of flexibility on their strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the funding provided by the United States Office of Naval Research (Grant N00014-08-1-0136), the materials provided by Gurit and Callaghan Innovation (formerly Industrial Research Limited), Auckland for providing access to testing facilities.

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